

Perceived Safety and Greenspace Access: Predicting Avoidance Behaviour in Leeds and Bradford Parks

Jennie Gray^{*1}, Victoria Houlden^{†1} and Anna Barker^{‡2}

¹ School of Geography, University of Leeds

² School of Law, University of Leeds

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Summary

Urban greenspace accessibility is fundamental to daily life; it improves health and wellbeing and gives us a place to connect. However, access to greenspaces is not equal, underserved communities continually lack greenspaces of sufficient size, quality, and diversity, that do not meet their social, cultural, or personal needs. This research focusses on one specific aspect of accessibility, *Acceptability* (see the 6A Framework for Equitable Greenspace Access), via predicting park avoidance in local parks and greenspaces. Results show differences in avoidance behaviour between demographics, highlighting the importance of considering intersectional dimensions of *Acceptability* both in greenspace accessibility research, and urban planning.

KEYWORDS: greenspace accessibility, spatial analysis, gender inequality

1. Introduction

Access to urban greenspace is credited with a range of benefits including physical health, mental wellbeing, and social cohesion (Houlden et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2021). While research increasingly acknowledges the importance of greenspace quality and awareness on use, most studies continue to focus on spatial indicators of access, including ‘Availability’ (quantity and size) and ‘Accessibility’ (ease of travel). Yet, specific populations (e.g. socioeconomically disadvantaged, ethnically and racially minoritised, disabled people, older adults, women, girls and families, LGBTQ) face barriers in a range of other greenspace access domains. The 6A Framework for Equitable Greenspace Access covers Availability, Accessibility, Accommodation, Affordability, Acceptability, and Awareness (6A-4EGA) – see **Table 1** for descriptions) (Gray et al., 2025).

Table 1 The 6 As of Accessibility

A of Accessibility	Description. Are greenspaces:
Availability	Available in sufficient size and quantity?
Accessibility	Easily reachable and navigable?
Accommodation	Meeting diverse user needs?
Affordability	Temporally and financially affordable?
Acceptability	Safe, and socially and culturally acceptable?
Awareness	Known to residents, supported by information enabling confident use?

This conceptual framework builds on Penchansky and Thomas’s (1981) 5 As of Accessibility, incorporates Saurman’s (2016) sixth A. It offers a comprehensive approach to accessibility and explicitly aligns improvements within the 6 dimensions to Fredman’s (2016) principles of substantive equality, offering a practical tool for urban planners and decision-makers (Gray et al., 2025).

* J.h.gray@leeds.ac.uk

† V.houlden@leeds.ac.uk

‡ A.barker@leeds.ac.uk

Acceptability is shaped by perceptions of safety and feelings of inclusion and belonging, making it a critical driver of accessibility. Research shows that when certain users perceive greenspaces as unsafe, they engage in ‘safety work’ to navigate risk (Vera-Gray and Kelly, 2020). For example, women are more likely to feel unsafe in parks, often modifying their routines by avoiding parks after dark or taking longer, alternative routes (Barker et al., 2025). This avoidance behaviour may serve as a more precise indicator of greenspace inequity than safety concerns alone. By understanding and modelling avoidance patterns, we can identify which populations are effectively excluded from the health, wellbeing and social benefits of greenspaces; insights essential for informing equitable park design, management, and interventions.

2. Methods

2.1 Survey Data

The Leeds and Bradford Parks and Greenspaces survey (April-June 2025) used online recruitment via targeted advertisements to reach diverse demographics, while paper surveys were stratified and mailed to 1,000 households in the most deprived 10% areas in each city. 3,000 postcard invitations (with QR code to the survey) were also randomly distributed in each city. In total, 2,682 valid responses were collected: 805 from Bradford, 1877 from Leeds.

Each response was geocoded to the respondent’s postcode centroid and their most used park (referred to hereafter as ‘their park’), enabling spatial analysis of park avoidance. This spatial linkage allowed exploration of patterns in relation to park location, geographic area, and demographic characteristics. The final dataset of variables is summarised in **Table 2**.

Table 2 Variable descriptions and data type. Derived from the Parks and Greenspaces survey unless otherwise stated.

Variable	Description	Type
ParkAvoidance	Does respondent regularly avoid their park.	Binary
Safety	Does respondent feel safe in their park in daytime.	Ordinal
Park_Welcoming	Does respondent feel welcome in their park.	Likert
Park_Satisfaction	How satisfied respondent is with their park.	Likert
VisitLength	How long the respondent visits their park.	Ordinal
Age	Respondent’s age in brackets.	Ordinal
Sex	Respondent’s sex.	Nominal
GenderIdentity	Respondent’s gender identity.	Nominal
SexualOrientation	Respondent’s sexual orientation.	Nominal
EthnicGroup	Respondent’s ethnicity.	Nominal
FinancialWellbeing	Respondent’s self-reported financial wellbeing.	Ordinal
GeneralHealth	Respondent’s self-reported general health.	Ordinal
Wellbeing	Respondent’s wellbeing, via short SWEMWBS.	Continuous
Religion	Respondent’s religion.	Nominal
EmploymentStatus	Respondent’s employment status.	Nominal
GardenAccess	Does respondent have garden access.	Ordinal
LongTermLimitingHealthCondition	Does respondent have a long-term limiting illness.	Binary
RUC	Respondent’s 2021 Rural Urban Classification (ONS)	Ordinal

Figure 1 displays the park locations derived from the survey responses, where park avoidance data are modelled.

Figure 1: Park locations

2.2 Methods

Our analysis followed a two-stage approach seen in park access research (McIntire et al., 2022), in which unadjusted bivariate analyses are first used to characterise group differences before fitting multivariate models. Since our data did not meet assumptions of normality, we used nonparametric tests: Kruskal-Wallis for overall group differences, and Dunn’s post hoc for pairwise comparisons. Effect sizes were calculated using Cliff’s delta, to quantify the magnitude and direction of group differences beyond statistical significance (Fiel Peres, 2026). All variables were entered into multivariate logistic regression (reflecting the binary nature of park the avoidance outcome) regardless of bivariate significance.

Future work will incorporate spatial data into multilevel models to account for hierarchical structure and spatial autocorrelation, allowing us to quantify how geographic context influences park avoidance beyond individual-level characteristics.

3. Initial Results

3.1 Statistical Analysis

Park avoidance varied significantly across demographics. By sex, regular avoidance was reported by 35% of males, 56% of females, and 64% of those who preferred not to disclose ($\chi^2(2) = 85.94$, $p < .001$), with small but reliable effects (Cliff’s delta -0.22 and -0.29), indicating a 61–67% probability that females or those who preferred not to disclose report greater avoidance than males. By age, avoidance was highest among 17–24-year-olds (70%) compared to 46–56% in older groups ($\chi^2(5) = 40.16$, $p < .001$), with small effects (0.18–0.28) suggesting younger adults are 56–64% more likely to report greater avoidance. Religion highlighted differences ($\chi^2(7) = 15.28$, $p = .033$): 46% of Christians

reported avoidance versus 66% among ‘other’ religions, a small effect (−0.21) corresponding to a 61% probability of greater avoidance among ‘other’ religions.

3.2 Predicting Park Avoidance

To analyse the combined and independent effects of demographic factors on park avoidance, we estimated a logistic regression model with demographics, area, and park-level predictors. The binary outcome captured regular avoidance. Odds ratios quantify the relative odds of avoidance in each group compared with a designated reference group. They are calculated by dividing the odds of the outcome group by the reference group, and therefore have no fixed minimum or maximums. Interpreting these ratios indicates the characteristics most strongly associated with avoidance behaviour.

The model identified several strong predictors of park avoidance, seen in **Table 3**. The most influential being strong disagreement with feeling the park is welcoming (OR = 5.24), indicating individuals are over 5x as likely to avoid parks than the reference group. Being female (OR = 2.57), of mixed ethnicity (OR = 2.24), or living in an urban area further from a major town or city (OR = 2.23) were also more than 2x likely to avoid parks, than being male, White, and urban nearer to town or city.

Conversely, lower odds of avoidance were observed for residents of larger rural areas further from major towns (OR = 0.15), people with Sikh religious affiliation (OR = 0.22), older adults (50-64 OR = 0.38), and respondents who reported feeling safe (OR = 0.50), indicating these groups are less likely to avoid parks than their reference groups.

Table 3 Logistic Regression Results: notable odds ratios in relation to *reference groups*.

Variable	Category	Odds Ratio
Park_Welcoming	Strongly disagree	5.24
	Disagree	1.37
	Agree	0.91
	Strongly agree	0.62
	<i>Neither</i>	
Safety	Unsafe	1.69
	Safe	0.50
	<i>Neutral</i>	
RUC	Urban further from major town/city	2.23
	Smaller rural further from major town/city	1.61
	Smaller rural nearer to major town/city	1.41
	Larger rural further from major town/city	0.15
	<i>Urban: Nearer to major town/city</i>	
Park_Satisfaction	Strongly disagree	0.54
	Disagree	1.12
	Agree	0.80
	Strongly agree	0.54
	<i>Neither</i>	
Sex	Female	2.57
	Prefer not to say	1.41
	<i>Male</i>	
Age	25-34	0.56
	35-49	0.48
	50-64	0.38

Religion	Over 65	0.50
	17-24	
	Jewish	1.35
	Christian	0.80
	Hindu	0.48
	Muslim	0.46
	Sikh	0.22
EthnicGroup	Any other religion	1.36
	No religion	
	Mixed	2.24
	South Asian	1.35
	Asian	1.05
	Black	0.80
	Other	1.23
FinancialWellbeing	White	
	In financial difficulty	0.76
	Struggling	1.03
	Getting by	1.22
	Living comfortably	0.90
	Doing ok	

4. Discussion and Conclusions

These initial findings show that perceptions of safety and welcomeness at the park level are the strongest predictors of park avoidance. Sex remains a critical determinant: women are more than twice as likely to avoid parks, highlighting persistent gendered safety concerns in public space. Age, religion, and ethnicity also play significant roles, suggesting that intersecting identities may compound barriers, making Acceptability a crucial dimension of greenspace accessibility. Spatial context appears influential too, with Rural–Urban Classifications linked to variation in avoidance patterns. Building on this, further work incorporates spatial elements into multilevel models to specifically examine the spatial interactions and neighbourhood-level effects on park avoidance. This includes assessing whether avoidance clusters spatially, testing for area-level random effects, and evaluating how park characteristics interact with neighbourhood context to shape avoidance behaviour.

Park avoidance itself is a novel outcome, rarely modelled in research. By identifying the demographic and contextual factors associated with avoidance, this study provides new evidence on an underexplored dimension of greenspace inequity and offers targeted insights to support local authorities in planning and interventions aimed at improving safety.

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Biographies

Jennie Gray is an ECR, working as a Research Fellow at the University of Leeds. She is interested in all facets of neighbourhood research, the sociodemographic processes cultivating changes, the spatiotemporal properties of those changes, and finally the human consequences of them, notably socio-spatial inequalities and their impacts on accessibility.

Victoria Houlden is an Associate Professor in Urban Data Science in the School of Geography, University of Leeds. She aims to understand the ways in which spaces and places embody inequalities, and the social structures influencing how people relate to their environment. Her current projects focus on greenspace access.

Anna Barker is an Associate Professor in Criminology & Criminal Justice in the School of Law, University of Leeds. Her research focuses on making public spaces feel safer and more inclusive, particularly for women. She currently leads the *Safer Parks: Improving Access for Women and Girls* programme.